

Occupational Stress and Burnout Syndrome among Surgical Specialists in Bulgaria

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ABSTRACT

When professional exhaustion and burnout occurs among healthcare professionals, it not only affects the health of healthcare professionals, it would also affect the health of many other people who are cared for by physicians, looking at the problem in this way, we see that it goes beyond of a profession and could affect anyone.

In our study, we are looking for this "modern" disease among the medics of an Eastern European country.

Keywords: Burnout syndrome, Occupational stress

INTRODUCTION:

Burnout syndrome occurs relatively often and has an economic and social burden on the individual as well as on society as a whole, and it is stable over time, making its prophylaxis even more significant. It is possible to avoid a burnout by organizing efforts in the work environment and health promotion events.

OBJECTIVES:

Our research is dedicated to this modern, socially significant, health problem. Burnout syndrome among surgeons has been studied, techniques and

measures have been proposed to solve it, but it still exists and is not fully resolved, which makes it particularly important, as well as our study. The study included 201 doctors working in surgical wards across the country.

We have investigated:

1. The link between the socio-demographic characteristics and the manifestation of professional stress and burnout syndrome.
2. Sources of stress for professionals working in surgical wards.
3. Factors to minimize stress in the workplace.
4. Social support as an essential element of coping strategies to address occupational

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stress.

5. Diseases of respondents in relation to acute or chronic stress.
6. Degrees of burnout syndrome in the examined individuals on the three scales (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, personal achievement).

The "Program for the Prevention and Management of Professional Stress and Burnout Syndrome in Doctors in Surgical Wards" has been proposed, which gives specific directions for action.

The leading contributions are in two strands, a theoretical-cognitive importance and a practical value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

1. The lack of professional incentives and motivation ranks first in the survey (62.7%). Females, young people (25-30 years and 41-50 years) and the specialties of obstetrics and gynecology, ENT and Anesthesiology and resuscitation to a greater extent assess the lack of motivation for the stress factor.
2. In second place among the sources of stress respondents put the microclimate in the work team (54.2%). Women are more aware of the microclimate in the team as a source of stress.
3. Poor organization of work in the workplace ranks third among sources of stress. Young people report this stressor to a greater extent - 71.4% of the respondents in the age group 25-30. and 61.5% of the respondents in the age group 31-40.
4. More than half of the respondents working in the obstetric wards (58.3%) and in the abdominal surgery wards (53.8%) assess the difficult communication with the management as a stressor.
5. Almost unanimously surveyed physicians place adequate pay for work and improving the organization of work in the

workplace (66.7%) as the most important and fundamental incentives for optimal professional realization and minimization of stress. 80% of the surveyed anesthesiologists believe that good pay will reduce stress at work and addiction is statistically significant.

6. 75% of obstetricians report the need to improve working conditions.
7. For 19.9% of doctors, setting realistic goals professionally is of paramount importance for overcoming personal professional stress.
8. Social support is a proven means of overcoming stress. The family is an anti-stress environment for 54.2% of the medics, the friends - for 32.3% and 10% of the respondents do not share their professional problems with anyone. Men are more likely to share professional problems with colleagues.
9. According to the respondents, the impact of stress agents on the health status of doctors working in surgical wards is inevitable. The analysis of the results shows that diseases of the circulatory system: hypertension and various arrhythmias (extrasystoles, tachycardia, etc.) are the most common health problems that are attributed to stress. To a lesser extent, respondents associate diseases of another nature with occupational stress: gastrointestinal diseases; diseases with autoimmune genesis: Hashimoto's thyroiditis and type 2 diabetes mellitus and diseases such as generalized anxiety and depressive episodes.
10. Doctors from surgical wards most often undertake the practice of hobbies (59.7%), communication with close people (52.2%), physical work, sports, tourism, walks (48.8%), other means (walks, shower) to deal with stress. , bath) 21.9%. It is worrying that 17.9% take sedatives and alcohol to copy stress, and 9.7% indulge in

uncontrolled eating. Only 6% use self-training techniques to deal with occupational stress (Fig. 18). Women are more likely to interact with friends and children to deal with stress.

11. Regarding the study of burnout syndrome on the Maslach scale, extremely high levels of emotional exhaustion (43.1%) and depersonalization were identified in the observed sample. 41.5% of the surveyed men show a high degree of burnout syndrome on the scale of emotional exhaustion, as well as a high degree on the scale of depersonalization (47.5%). In women, a high degree of burnout is observed, especially on the scale of emotional exhaustion. The largest percentage of those studied in the specialty of abdominal surgery show a high degree of emotional exhaustion, followed by the subjects in the specialty of general surgery. The highest levels on the scale for depersonalization show the respondents with a specialty in general surgery (32.8%), followed by the respondents with a specialty in abdominal surgery (30.8%).

CONCLUSIONS:

The conducted own researches give the chance to formulate the following conclusions:

1. The specifics of the medical work of doctors, working in surgical wards, turns them into a risk contingent in terms of the impact of occupational stress, leading to changes in their mental and physiological condition.
2. Lack of incentives and motivation at work are a major source of occupational stress in respondents.
3. The bad microclimate in the work team has a stressful effect on the doctors from the surgical wards.
4. Poor work organization in the workplace is a risk factor for occupational stress.

5. Surgeons are at high risk for burnout. There are high degrees of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization among the subjects.
6. Measures are needed at various levels for the prevention and early management of occupational stress and burnout syndrome.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Proper organization and management of material and financial resources through:
 - Securing the funds for labor activity;
 - Material incentives;
 - Improving working conditions;
 - Social benefits;
2. Creation and introduction of anti-stress programs, including medical preventive activities, monitoring of changes in the work environment and the danger of "burnout", acquaintance with the ways to successfully deal with stress in the workplace;
3. Individual stress management by developing personal relaxation skills.
4. Proper organization and management of human resources through:
 - optimal organization of work;
 - training and education of staff in a healthy lifestyle and work;
 - creating a good psycho-climate.

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE STUDY:

Theoretical and cognitive contribution:

1. The literature review examines the genesis of occupational stress and burnout syndrome, their impact on the health of employees in health care organizations, as well as known techniques for prevention and relief of these conditions;
2. A study of occupational stress in physicians working in surgical wards was conducted, examining the sources and its

effects on the health of study participants;

3. The manifestations of burnout syndrome on its three scales were studied through the Maslach Burnout Inventory in doctors working in surgical wards;
4. A program for prevention and management of occupational stress and burnout syndrome in doctors in surgical wards is proposed:

Contribution to practice:

1. Proposals and recommendations have been formulated to the interested persons and the managers of the medical establishments for prevention and relief of the states of stress and burnout syndrome;
2. The established regularities provide a basis for future research on the topic.

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DECLARATION: I declare that this article has not been published elsewhere.

Conflicts of Interest: Nil